

STEAM EDUCATION METHODOLOGY FOR PRESCHOOL CHILDREN'S SCHOOL PREPARATION USING DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES

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Abstract. This article contributes to STEAM education and preschool readiness by teaching preschoolers to Steam using modern learning platforms, websites, author-created websites, and computer programs. Information about computer programs designed to keep children busy and develop memory, reasoning, and logic; programs that teach children the alphabet of multiple languages; and websites and platforms that address child development. Offers. This article describes how the STEAM teaching methodology was born and what its methodological foundations are based on.

Key words. Steam, Press-school, digital technologies, methodology, methods, computer programs, platforms, site, pandemic era.

Introduction. The pandemic era has laid the groundwork for distance learning, the development of e-learning, and the creation of various applications to help children reach their full potential and work online more efficiently. From the youngest to the oldest, everyone worked and studied online. Even preschoolers tried to grab araphrased Text Website, school preparation, acquisition of knowledge. Of course, mobile technology, computer Internet and wireless Internet Wi-Fi connectivity have played an important role in this. Preschool children began learning the materials they needed on age- and intellectually-appropriate sites and platforms with parents, nurses, Methodists, and preschool educators. They tried digital reading in the environment, mathematics, and all sciences using digital technology. It was recommended to teach children about geometric figures, properties of objects and their appearance using various computer games. Every scholar, every Methodist educator was looking for a platform or website dedicated to children to prepare their children and grandchildren.

Every registered person can take her 10 free lessons for children. It will be possible. By learning these exercises, your child will get her 10 tasks a day. It was recommended to teach children about geometric figures, properties of objects and their appearance using various computer games. Every scholar, every Methodist educator was looking for a platform or website dedicated to children to prepare their children and grandchildren. Her one such platform is her iQsha.ru platform, where anyone who registers can take her 10 free lessons for their children. By learning these exercises, your child will get her 10 tasks a day. Users who do not wish to wait will be charged for receipt of her order quick. Users who do not wish to wait will be charged for receiving the quick order. Faced with such challenges, we are looking not only for platforms in this field, but also for the education of preschool and school-age children, the work of scientists and educators, and their education and methods. I am also looking for research. And created a compact methodology, created 18 computer programs for preschoolers to strengthen them, created a website on children's preparation for school using information technology, and created the University of Uzbekistan Namangan We tested them at the State Information Test Center. Nominated for her 100 innovative projects of the Republic of Uzbekistan "Most innovative projects in the field of education".

A computer program for fragmented corpses. Teach your child to break down objects into parts and put them together to form a whole. Before that, we used the famous "gift" of literary savvy pedagogy F. Fröbel, who created and built the first preschool institution for pedagogical children. Based on the use of E.'s board. Building on Segen and M. Montessori and the notion that if these panels developed mental retardation, then these panels could also develop mental retardation, we took this hypothesis further and scientifically engaged in research. On a board by E. Segen and M. Montessori, I created a computer program in the form of a game in which children were placed in an open space and filled with geometric shapes, mathematical figures, animals and fruits on the board. Three numbers for sorting languages. and vice versa. Our other hypothesis was that the use of computer games in preschool children helps them prepare for school, explore their surroundings, and move more freely in society.

Literature review. F. Frobel provided a set of toys to teach children, on which they performed exercises. At its bottom appeared colored woolen balloons hanging on strings, and children used these balloons in different directions. I had to move. In the next exercise, replace these colored balls with his three objects that the children are currently using: a ball, a cube and a cylinder hanging from a string. In each series of exercises, children are required to create different life forms out of cubes or blocks and are also asked to make "nice shapes". This process was done manually by children and

had to be done on the computer in computer games. To create these processes and come up with such ideas, we considered and analyzed various sources and literature.³⁸ We have used the following educational resources to encourage Methodist educators to engage with their children and do the same. Comprehensive Prep for Children has created a website with a variety of texts and resources.

Children using these programs. We have organized our lessons according to individual and group teaching methods. Our site contains several programs:

"Memory Sharpening Program", "Trilingual Alphabet Teaching Program", "Inventor" Computer Program That Makes Sense to Teach Children.

The result of this research and effort was the creation of a website and a computer program embedded within it. That is:

A computer program called "computer + attention + memory + reasoning" was created to enhance memory see. How to teach the Trilingual Alphabet:

Uzbek, Russian and English "trilingual computer program:

Uzbek, Russian, English" (8, - p. 11], [8, - p. 12] cf.); 14 computer programs were developed for F. Fröbel's preschool activities, d.H. What he called "gifts". Computer programs for teaching methods involving mathematics, promoted by E. Segen and M. Montessori, have been developed and we propose to implement them through STEAM educational programs. Comprehensive Prep for Children created a website using a variety of texts and resources, using the domain and hosting of the NamSU website, installing and creating computer programs thereon, and attending school using these programs; Hosted his one-off training session for previous kids. We have organized our lessons according to individual and group teaching methods. Our site contains several programs:

Analysis and results. "Memory Sharpening Program", "Trilingual Alphabet Teaching Program", "Inventor" Computer Program That Makes Sense to Teach Children Experiments were performed and results were calculated using the mathematical statistical chi-square method. Considering the data obtained after carrying out experiments in our study, using the method of mathematical statistics chi-square, looking at tables of experimental data, applying formulas and formulas for processing experimental data Draw a diagram. The level of knowledge of children when teaching children in the traditional way according to the program "Ilk Kadam" - "first steps".

³⁸ [9].Burkhanova M.G.(2021).SOCIO-PHILOSOPHICAL LOOK OF A CULTURAL MAN.ISJ Theoretical &Applied Science,12(104),422-425.<https://dx.doi.org/10.15863/TAS.2021.02.94.6> Doi:

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Discussion. We encourage you to use STEAM education, his gift with e-learning, a computer program that we have created, to teach preschool children the exercises of F. Froebel. In addition, it is recommended to develop children's intellectual abilities and mathematical thinking with the help of blessing boards³⁹. At the same time, at this level of training, F. Fröbel, E. Segen board, computer game on it. With the help of the game, children find and put on the board the geometric shapes "window", "fruit?", "vegetables", "letters", "vegetables", letters, numbers. The game consists of several parts.

Conclusion. Thus, preparing children for school by developing their mental abilities in the direction of STEM with the help of computer programs and existing platforms and pages created in pre-school institutions. becomes possible. Students can use the Kuth Method in extracurricular and circle classes or other activities, depending on the child's age and mental ability. For this purpose, it is recommended to open pre-school and school informatics departments in higher education institutions. Proposing sites that incorporate such programs into the teaching of "Information Technology in Preschool and Primary Education" at the higher education level, as well as proposing the creation and use of sites for teaching in this field, remains It Is difficult. 'lib remains. Therefore, the period itself should not only show such programs to students, but also create such programs for them.

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